

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF A SCREW PRESS BRIQUETTING MACHINE

Arowosafe, K. O.*¹, Kamal A. R.¹, Ola, O. A.¹ and Olayinka M.²

¹Farm Power and Machinery Department

²Engineering and Scientific Service Department

National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's E-mail Address: karowosafe@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The disposal of the enormous quantity of agro-residues produced either at the point of post-harvest, or after consumption poses great challenge not just to the farmers but the entire populace. These wastes are either left to decay or are burned in the open field thereby causing an extensive pollution and menace to the environment because an adequate means of turning this wastes to a beneficial alternative is not popular in this part of the world. As a solution to this problem, a screw press briquetting machine was designed and fabricated with its main feedstock being agro-residues. The principles of machine design according to Khurmi and Gupta (2005) were adopted to design the essential component parts of the machine; hopper, screw barrel, the die, and screw conveyor. The machine has a screw diameter of 50 mm and runs on a 415/15HP/3phase electric motor with a pulley diameter of 10mm/550mm. The belt designation is machine is B68. The design and fabrication of the screw press briquetting machine was successfully carried out. The machine can be easily maintained without any technicality and all materials used for the fabrication are locally available in the case of worn - out parts.

KEYWORDS: Agro residues, biomass extruder, machine design, briquette

1. INTRODUCTION

The concern arising from environmental pollution, protection of forestry resources, which act as major absorbers of CO₂; and the ever-increasing deforestation, along with the increase in the consumption of wood fuels; and the high cost and shortage of conventional fuel such as kerosene and cooking gas, are the key factors leading to the quest to diversify the energy and economic powers of individual households through the use of alternative fuel. Similarly, the disposal of the enormous quantity of agro-residues generated either at the point of post-harvest, or after consumption poses great challenge to the farmers.

Several attempts have been made to manage these wastes mostly by open field burning or sometimes left to decompose at their production or consumption areas thereby causing an extensive pollution, and menace

to the environment (Jekayinfa and Omisakin, 2005).

The use of raw agricultural residues as energy feedstock have many disadvantages which include: difficulty in controlling the rate of burning, large volume or area required for storage, and problems in its transportation and distribution. Apart from the problems of transportation, storage, and handling, the direct burning of loose biomass in conventional grates is associated with very low thermal efficiency and widespread air pollution (Oladeji, 2012).

One of the viable and promising technologies being actively pursued worldwide by which agricultural and other biomass residues can be converted to biomass energy is through the process of briquetting (Wilaipon, 2008). Briquetting is the process of densification of residues into a product of higher density than

the original raw materials often with the aid of a binder. According to Oladeji and Enweremadu (2012), briquetting of biomass improves its handling characteristics, increases the volumetric calorific value, reduces transportation costs and makes it available for a variety of application such as fuel for industrial and local uses. Biomass briquettes are made from combustible materials obtained from agricultural, forestry waste or coal dust, bound together and compressed into small pieces. Briquettes have better physical properties and combustion rate than the initial waste and serve as compliments to firewood and charcoal for domestic cooking and agro-industrial operations, thereby reducing the high demand for both, and serve as a global warming countermeasure by conserving forestry resources.

Briquette machines have been in existence and used for sawdust and waste materials in Europe, Asia, and America (Osarenmwinda and Ihenyen, 2012) even in Africa, but in managing wastes generated on the farm, much attention has not been given to it in Nigeria hence, the objective of this study is to develop and construct a screw press briquetting machine with the main feedstock being agricultural residue such as corn curb, rice bran, groundnut husk, saw dust etc.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The machine design for briquetting was of single extrusion screw press type. The machine consists mainly of the following component parts: frame, hopper, 15hp electric motor, pulley and belts, screw, barrel, die. The machine design was carried out using principles of engineering design with due consideration to cost, ease of operation, serviceability and durability.

2.1 Design of the Machine

From review of literatures some assumptions were set for the design of the machine. These assumptions are based on forces required to drive the shaft, throughput capacity, dynamic load on bearing, diameter of the screw shaft, the dynamic load on the bearing transmitted by the screw shaft, power of the electric motor required to compact pulverized biomass as well as extrude the resultant briquette from the die, adaptability of design and fitness for purpose, design acceptability based on socio-cultural practices. The orthographic, exploded and isometric views of the machine are shown from Figures 1 to 5.

Fig 1. Side view

Fig. 2. Front view

Fig 3. Top view

Fig 4. Exploded view of the screw press briquetting machine

Fig. 5. Isometric view of the briquette screw press

2.1.1 Frame

The frame is made of mild steel angle iron and function as to give support to the whole assembly unit. Rankins's formula was employed in the design of the frame.

$$W_{cr} = f \times \frac{A}{1} + a \left(\frac{Le}{k} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where, W_{cr} = crippling load, a = Rankins's constant for mild steel material, K = radius of gyration

2.1.2 Volume of hopper, (V_h)

The hopper is considered as squared frustum made of mild steel and the volume was calculated according Ajieh *et al.* (2016).

$$Vh = \frac{h}{3} (A + (A + A^1 + \sqrt{AA^1})) \quad (2)$$

Where, h = height of the hopper, A = area of the large base, A^1 = is the area of the small base

2.2 Screw Geometry

According to the equations reported by Potente *et al.* (1994), the screw geometry as shown in Figure 4 which includes: channel depth, screw pitch, pitch angle, flight width and channel width were designed. Also, the relationship between the outer screw diameter and the distance between the axis of a flight screw, screw pitch (t), intermeshing angle (α), angle of pitch (ϕ_s), channels width (b_{max}), flight angle (β) and depth (h_{max}) were computed from Equations (3) to (9) (Fadeyibi *et al.*, 2016).

Fig 4. Screw Geometry

D = barrel diameter (mm), D_s = distance between axis of flight screws (mm), d = shaft diameter (mm), t = pitch length (mm), b = channel width (mm), ϵ = pitch of helix (mm),

ϕ_s = helix angle (deg.).

2.2.1 Distance between axis of flight screw, (mm)

$$\frac{a}{D_s} \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \quad (3)$$

2.2.2 Screw pitch, mm

$$t = \frac{2\pi L_{kn}}{\delta j_{kn}} \quad (4)$$

2.2.3 Pitch angle, (ϕ_s), Deg/ rad

$$\phi_s = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{t}{\pi D_s} \right) \quad (5)$$

2.2.4 Flight angle, β , (Deg/rad)

$$\beta = \frac{\pi}{i} - \alpha \quad (6)$$

2.2.5 Channel width, (h_{max}), Mm

$$h_{max} = D_s - a \quad (7)$$

2.2.6 Channel width, (b_{max}), Mm

$$b_{max} = t \cos \phi_s - \epsilon_{max} \quad (8)$$

2.2.7 Intermeshing angle, (α)

$$\alpha = 2 \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{a}{D_2} \right) \quad (9)$$

Where, $L_{kn} = 28$ mm right handed standard screw, $\delta = 1.57$ radians, $j_{kn} =$ standard screw element = 2, $\alpha =$ distance between axis of flight (mm).

2.2.8 Helix Angle of the Screw Conveyor

The helix of most screw extruders is usually made up of a uniform pitch of 43 mm (Fadeyibi *et al.*, 2016), and this is as well considered in the present design (Figure 1). The helix angle of the screw Extruder was determined using the equations computed by Roberts (2001).

$$A_e = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{P}{\pi D} \times \frac{R_o}{R_e} \right) \quad (10)$$

Where, A_e = Helix angle, R_o = Outer radius of screw = 50 mm (0.05 m), R_i = Inner radius of screw diameter = 40mm (0.04 m), R_e = Effective radius of screw, P = Screw pitch = 80 mm (0.08 m)

$$R_e = \frac{2}{3} \left[\frac{(R_o^3 - R_i^3)}{(R_o^2 - R_i^2)} \right] \quad (11)$$

2.3 Screw Barrel Design

According to Sivakumaran and Goodman (1986), the barrel was designed based on internal pressure, (P_b). The tangential stress, (σ), perpendicular to the axis of the cylinder is as given in Equation (12).

$$\sigma = \frac{2P_b D_b^2}{(D_1^2) - (D_2^2)} \quad (12)$$

Allowable tangential stress is assumed to be 140MPa

2.4 Drive and Driven Pulley Data

2.4.1 Pulley Diameter

Power is transmitted from the electric motor to the shaft of the extruding unit through the belt and pulley. For this purpose, B-belt was selected due to its ability to absorb shocks against the effects of forces of vibration; its flexibility and cost of maintenance (Fadeyibi *et al.*, 2016).

The diameter of the pulley of the screw shaft was computed as presented:

$$D_2 D_1 = N_2 N_1 \quad (13)$$

Given: N_1 = speed of motor, (rpm), D_1 = diameter of the motor pulley, (mm), D_2 = diameter of the screw shaft pulley, (mm), N_2 = speed of the screw shaft

$$V_{\text{belt}} = \frac{\pi D N}{60} \quad (14)$$

Where, V_{belt} = belt speed, (m/s), D = diameter of the motor pulley, (mm) N = speed of the motor, (rev/min)

2.4.3 Belt Length

The belt length is computed as:

$$X = 2C + 1.57(D_1 + D_2) + (D_1 + D_2)/4Ca \quad (15)$$

Where, X = belt length, (m), Ca = assumed center distance between pulley, (mm), D_1 = pitch diameter of drive pulley, (mm), D_2 = pitch diameter of driven pulley, (mm)

2.4.4 Power Requirement for Motor Selection

Khurmi and Gupta (2005), computed the power required by the screw conveyor with the expression shown in Equations (16) and (17).

$$P_{sc} = 0.7355ClQ \quad (16)$$

where, P_{sc} = power required by the screw conveyor, (KW), C = constant coefficient for conveyed material usually taken to be 0.3, l = length of the screw conveyor, assumed to be 400 mm; 20 mm was isolated for clearance from the extrusion barrel.

The extrusion barrel pressure was computed from using:

$$P = \frac{P_{sc}}{Q_f} \quad (17)$$

Given, P = Pressure inside the extrusion barrel, (N/m^2), P_{sc} = power available to the screw conveyor, (kW), Q_f = flow rate of material, kg/s.

2.5 Working Mechanism of the Machine

Power is transmitted through pulley and belts from the electric motor which converts electrical energy into useful rotational motion of the screw. During extrusion, the biomass moves from the hopper which is conical in shape and welded to the screw barrel which houses the screw. The screw conveys, grinds and compresses the material into the die with substantial pressure with the help of a rotating screw through the barrel and compacts it against a die which causes substantial pressure build-up and friction, along the screw owing to biomass shearing. The combined effects of wall friction at the barrel, internal friction in the material, and high rotational speed (~600 rpm) of the screw, increase the temperature in the closed system and heat the biomass causing the release of lignin resident in the biomass which serves as binder (in the case of saw dust). This heated biomass is then forced through the extrusion die to form the briquettes.

3. TESTING OF THE MACHINE

The design and fabrication of the screw press briquetting machine was successfully carried out with locally sourced materials as shown in figures 6. The machine is very applicable for local production, operation, repair and maintenance. From the theoretical formulations drawn from the design consideration, the machine parameters and specifications are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Machine Parameters and specifications of Screw Extruder

Parameters	Value
Hopper Design Data	
Volume of hopper, m ³	0.019
Screw Design Geometry	
Screw shaft diameter, mm	50
Distance between axis of flight screw, mm	0.044
Screw pitch, mm	37.5
Flight angle, β , (Deg/rad)	0.012
Channel width, (h_{max}), mm	0.015
Helix angle of the screw conveyor, deg	18.65
Power and Drive Pulley Data	
Electric Motor	415/15HP/3phase
Pulley Diameter, mm	10/550
Belt Speed, m/s	2.225
Belt Length, m	12.5/1450
Belt Designation	B68
No. of belts required	2

The machine was tested to determine its production capability. Materials used in the test include the machine, sawdust, container, cassava starch, steel tape and stop watch. In the test, an ingredient ratio of the mixture is 75% sawdust, 10% cassava starch and 8% water. The briquette produced by the machine shown in Figure 7 is cylindrical in shape and has an average length of 250 mm with a centre hole. The machine has a low production cost because it is designed to have fewer number of parts that are readily available.

Fig. 6. Screw extruder briquette machine

Fig. 7. Briquette samples

4. CONCLUSION

The screw press briquetting machine is principally for converting agro-residues such as, corn cobs, corn stalk, rice bran etc. to fuel briquette for energy generation. From the test carried out, the machine is capable of producing briquette in continuous operation which gives it an edge over the manually operated hydraulic press. It can be adapted to curb agro residues indiscriminate disposal and burning in their production or consumption centres thereby protecting the environment from air pollution and invariably turning waste to wealth.

REFERENCES

- Ajieh, M. U., Igboanugo A. C. and Audu T. O. K. (2016). Design of Grass Briquette Machine. *Nigerian Journal of Technology (NIJOTECH)* Vol. 35, No. 3, pp. 527–530.
- Bhandari, V. B. (2010). Design of machine element, edition-3, 2010, Tata McGraw Hill publication, ISBN: 978-0-07068179-8.
- Fadeyibi, A., Osunde Z. D., Agidi, G. and Egwim, E. C. (2016). Design of single screw extruder for homogenizing bulk solids. *AgricEngInt: CIGR Journal Open access at <http://www.cigrjournal.org>* Vol. 18, No. 4.
- Jekayinfa, S. O. and Omisakin, O. S. (2005): The Energy Potentials of some agricultural wastes as local fuel materials in Nigeria. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR E-journal of Scientific Research and Development* Vol. VII, Manuscript EE 05 003:10p.
- Khurmi, R. S. and J. K. Gupta. (2005). A Text Book of Machine Design, Eurasia Publishing House (PVT.) Ltd. Pp. 1-1251.
- Oladeji, J. T. (2012), Comparative Study of Briquetting of Few Selected Agro-Residues Commonly Found in Nigeria *Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, 13(2):80 - 86.
- Oladeji, J. T. and Enweremadu, C. C. (2012). The Effects of Some Processing Parameters on Physical and Densification Characteristics of Corncob Briquettes. *International Journal of Energy Engineering*, 2(1):22 - 27.
- Osarenmwinda, J. O. and Ihenyen, O. I. (2012). The preliminary design of a manually operated briquetting machine. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.* Vol. 16 (2) 209–211.
- Potente H., Hanhart, W. and Reski, T. (1994). Design and Processing Optimization of Extruder Screws. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 34 (11):937 - 945.
- Sivakumaran, K. and Goodman, J. W. (1986). Influence of internal pressure on performance of a small screw expeller. *Trans. of ASAE*, 28(1), 2801.
- Wilaipon P. (2008) “The Effect of Briquetting Pressure on Banana-Peel Briquette and the Banana Waste in Northern Thailand”. *American Journal of Applied Science*, 6(1):167 - 171.